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Anowar's Handbook of Electrical and Electronics Engineering

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for electrical engineers, textile engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of *Electrical and Electronics Engineering*. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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EEE-201, Elements of Electrical and
Electronics Engineering

Course instructor:

Engr. Tahmina Begum.

CSE Department.

*** Write down the definition of Electronics? ***

Ans: The Branch of engineering which deals with
efficient conduction through a vacuum or gas or
semi conductor is known as electronics.

Electronics essentially deals with electronic
devices and their utilization.

Ex: Radio, Telephone, cell phones, Television etc.

Importance:

1. Rectification
2. Amplification
3. Control
4. Generation
5. Conversion light into electricity
6. Conversion electricity into light.

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Rectification:

The conversion of a.c into d.c is called rectification.

Electronic devices can convert a.c power into d.c power with very efficiency.

This d.c supply can be used for charging storage batteries, field supply of d.c generators, electroplating etc.

Amplification:

The process of raising the strength of a weak signal is known as amplification. Electronic devices can accomplish the job of amplification and thus act as amplifiers.

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The amplifiers are used in a wide variety of ways. For example, an amplifier is used in a radio set where the weak is amplified so that it can be heard loudly. Similarly, amplifiers are used in public address system, television etc.

Control:

Electronic devices find wide applications in automatic control.

For example, speed of motor, voltage across a refrigerator etc. can be automatically controlled with the help of such devices.

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Generation :

Electronic devices can convert d.c power into a.c power of any frequency.

When performing this function, they are known as oscillators. The oscillators are used in a wide variety of ways. For example, electronic high frequency heating is used for annealing and hardening.

Conversion of light into electricity :

Electronic devices can convert light into electricity. This conversion of light into electricity is known as photo electricity.

photo-electric devices are used in Burglar alarms, sound recording on motion pictures etc.

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Conversion of electricity into light:

Electronic devices can convert electricity into light. This valuable property is utilized in television and radars.

Valence Electrons:

The electrons in the outermost orbit of an atom are known as valence electrons. The outermost orbit can have a maximum of 8 electrons i.e. the maximum number of valence electrons can be 8. The valence electrons determine the physical and chemical properties of a material.

→ These electrons determine whether or not the material is chemically active, metal or non-metal or a gas or solid.

→ These electrons also determine the electrical properties of a material.

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On the basis of electrical conductivity,

materials are generally classified into

- (a) conductors.
- (b) Insulators
- (c) Semi conductors

(a) Conductors:

When the number of valence electrons of an atom is less than 4 (i.e. half of the maximum eight electrons), the material is usually a metal and a conductor.

- Ex:
- $\text{Na} \rightarrow 1$ valence electrons
 - $\text{Mg} \rightarrow 2$ " "
 - $\text{Al} \rightarrow 3$ " "

Na

Mg

Al

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(b) Insulator: when the number of valence electrons of an atom is more than 4, the material is usually a non-metal and an insulator.

Ex: N → 5 valence electrons
S → 6 " "
Ne → 8 " "

N
(Nitrogen)

S (Sulphur)

Ne
(Neon)

(c) Semi conductor: when the number of valence electrons of an atom is 4 (i.e. exactly one-half of the maximum 8 electrons). The material has both metal and non metal properties and is usually a semiconductor.

Ex: Carbon - Silicon. Germanium

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Free electrons: The valence electrons which are very loosely attached to the nucleus are known as free electrons. The free electrons can be easily removed or detached by applying a small amount of external energy.

On the basis of free electron conductor, insulators and semiconductors can be defined as under.

conductor: A conductor is a substance which has a large number of free electrons. When potential difference is applied across a conductor, the free electrons move

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towards the positive terminal of supply,
constituting electric current.

Insulator: An insulator is a substance which has practically no free electrons at ordinary temp. Therefore, an insulator does not conduct current under the influence of potential difference.

Semiconductor: A semiconductor is a substance which has very few free electrons at room temp. Consequently, under the influence of potential difference, a semiconductor practically conducts no current.

Voltage source: Any device that produces voltage output continuously is known as a voltage source.

Direct voltage source: A device which produces direct voltage output continuously is called a direct voltage source.

Ex: cells
d.c generators

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characteristics: Maintain the same polarity of the output voltage i.e positive and negative terminals

do remain the same

Load current, $I = \frac{E_g}{R_L + R_i}$

Terminal voltage, $V = (E_g - IR_i)$ or IR_L

where,

E_g = D.C source

R_L = Load resistance

R_i = Internal resistance

Mathematics: A d.c source generating 500v has an internal resistance of 1000Ω. Find load current if load resistance is (i) 10Ω and (ii) 100Ω

Here,

d.c source, $E_g = 500V$

Internal resistance, $R_i = 1000\Omega$

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Load resistance, $R_{L1} = 10\Omega$

$R_{L2} = 1000\Omega$

Load current, $I_2 = ?$

$$\therefore \text{Load current, } I_1 = \frac{E_g}{R_i + R_{L1}} = \frac{500}{1000 + 10} = 0.495 \text{ A}$$

$$\text{Load current, } I_2 = \frac{E_g}{R_i + R_{L2}} = \frac{500}{1000 + 1000} = 0.25 \text{ A}$$

Alternating voltage source: A device which continuously produces alternating voltage output continuously is known as alternating voltage source.

Ex: a.c. generator

characteristics:

It periodically reverses the polarity of the output voltage.

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$$\text{Load current, } I = \frac{E_g}{Z_L + Z_i}$$

$$\text{Terminal voltage, } V = (E_g - IZ_i) \text{ or } IZ_L$$

where,

E_g = A.C source

Z_i = Internal Impedance

Z_L = Load impedance

Mathematics: An A.C Generator produces 50V has an internal impedance of 100Ω . Find load current if load impedance 50Ω .

Here, A.C source, $E_g = 50V$

Internal Impedance, $Z_i = 100\Omega$

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Load impedance, $Z_L = 50\Omega$

Load current, $I = ?$

$$I = \frac{E_g}{Z_i + Z_L} = \frac{150}{100 + 50} = \frac{150}{150} = 1.0 \text{ A}$$

Atomic structure

*** What do you understand by Energy bands?

Ans: The range of energies possessed by an electron in a solid is known as energy band.

Ex: Show the structure of Silicon

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*** What do you understand by Valence Band?

Ans: The range of energies (i.e. band) possessed by valence electrons is known as valence band.

The electrons in the outermost orbit of an atom are known as valence electrons.

In case of inert gases, the valence band is full whereas for other materials, it is only partially filled.

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Insulators:

Insulators (e.g. wood, glass etc) are those substances which do not allow the passage of electric current through them.

Conductors: Conductors (e.g. copper, aluminium) are those substances which easily allow the passage of electric current through them.

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Semiconductor : Semiconductors (e.g. germanium, Silicon etc) are those substances whose electrical conductivity lies between conductors and insulators.

Course instructor : Engr. Toriqul Islam

CSE Dept.

Ohm's law : The ratio of potential difference (V) between any two points on a conductor to the current (I) flowing through them, is constant, provided that temperature of the conductor does not change.

In other words, $\frac{V}{I} = \text{Constant}$

or, $\frac{V}{I} = R$ where R is the resistance of the conductor.

Resistance in Series:

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- (1) Current is the same through all three conductors
- (2) Voltage drop across each is different due to its different resistance and is given by ohm's law.
- (3) Sum of all three voltage drop is equal to the voltage applied across the three conductors.

$$V = V_1 + V_2 + V_3$$
$$= IR_1 + IR_2 + IR_3$$

But $V = IR$

$$\therefore IR = IR_1 + IR_2 + IR_3$$

$$\Rightarrow R = R_1 + R_2 + R_3$$

Voltage Divider Rule:

Total resistance, $R = R_1 + R_2 + R_3 = 2 + 4 + 6 = 12\Omega$

$$V_1 = V \cdot \frac{R_1}{R} = 24 \times \frac{2}{12} = 4 \text{ Volts}$$

$$V_2 = V \cdot \frac{R_2}{R} = 24 \times \frac{4}{12} = 8 \text{ Volts}$$

$$V_3 = V \cdot \frac{R_3}{R} = 24 \times \frac{6}{12} = 12 \text{ Volts}$$

$$\therefore V = V_1 + V_2 + V_3 = 4 + 8 + 12 = 24 \text{ Volts}$$

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Resistance in Parallel :

- ① Potential difference across all resistance is same. (V)
- ② Current in each resistor is different and is given by ohm's law.
- ③ The total current is the sum of the three separate current.

$$I = I_1 + I_2 + I_3 = \frac{V}{R_1} + \frac{V}{R_2} + \frac{V}{R_3}$$

Now, $I = \frac{V}{R}$

$$\therefore \frac{V}{R} = \frac{V}{R_1} + \frac{V}{R_2} + \frac{V}{R_3}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{R} = \frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2} + \frac{1}{R_3}$$

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Marko Distribution

Attendance - 10

Quiz - 20

Mid - 30

Final - 40

Current divider Rule:

For figure, two resistance are joined in parallel across a voltage V .

The current in each branch, as given by Ohm's law,

$$I_1 = \frac{V}{R_1}, I_2 = \frac{V}{R_2}$$

$$\therefore \frac{I_1}{I_2} = \frac{R_2}{R_1}$$

$$\text{Now, } I_1 + I_2 = I \therefore I_2 = I - I_1$$

$$\therefore \frac{I_1}{I - I_1} = \frac{R_2}{R_1}$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 R_1 = R_2 (I - I_1)$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 R_1 = I R_2 - I_1 R_2$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 (R_1 + R_2) = I R_2$$

$$\therefore I_1 = I \times \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2}$$

Similarly,

$$I_2 = I \times \frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2}$$

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Mathematical term :- 01

Resistance in Parallel circuit

Ques:-

What is the value of unknown resistor R if

the voltage drop across 500 ohm resistor is 2.5V

Ans:

According to voltage divider rule, drop

across 50 ohm

$$= 2.5 \times \frac{50}{500} = 0.25 \text{ V}$$

$$\text{Drop across CD or ED} = 2.5 + 0.25$$

$$= 2.75 \text{ V}$$

$$\text{Drop across } 550 \Omega = (12 - 2.75) \text{ V} = 9.25 \text{ V}$$

$$\therefore I = \frac{9.25}{550} = 0.0168 \text{ A}$$

$$I_2 = \frac{2.5}{500} = 0.005 \text{ A}$$

$$\therefore I_1 = I - I_2 = (0.0168 - 0.005) \text{ A} = 0.0118 \text{ A}$$

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$R = \frac{V}{I} = \frac{2.75}{0.118} \Omega = 233\Omega$

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Mathematical term: 02
 $R = \frac{V}{I} = \frac{2.75}{0.118} \Omega = 233\Omega$

Ex. 3.2: calculate the effective resistance of the following combination of resistances and the voltage drop across each resistance, when a potential difference of 10V is applied between point A and B.

Ans: Resistance between A & C = $3 \parallel 6 = 2\Omega$ [$R = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2}}$]

Resistance of ACD = $2 + 18 = 20\Omega$ [$R = R_1 + R_2$]

Now, there are two parallel paths between point A & D of resistance 20Ω & 5Ω

Resistance A & D = $20 \parallel 5 = 4\Omega$

Resistance A & B = $4 + 8 = 12\Omega$

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Total circuit current = $\frac{60}{12} = 5A$

Current through 5Ω resistance = $5 \times \frac{20}{20+5}$ [I = V * $\frac{R_2}{R_1+R_2}$]

Current through ACD = $5 \times \frac{5}{20+5} = 1A$

Potential Difference across 3Ω & 6Ω = $1 \times 2 [V=IR]$
= 2V

P.D across 18Ω = $1 \times 18 = 18V$

P.D across 5Ω = $4 \times 5 = 20V$

P.D across 8Ω = $5 \times 8 = 40V$

Electric charge :

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DC Network theorem:

Circuit: A circuit is a closed conducting path through which an electric current either flows or is intended to flow.

Linear circuit: A linear circuit is one whose parameters are constant i.e. they do not change with voltage or current.

Non-Linear circuit: It is that circuit whose parameters change with voltage or current.

Bilateral circuit: A Bilateral circuit is one whose properties or characteristics are the same in either direction.

Unilateral circuit: It is that circuit whose properties or characteristics change with the direction of its operation.

Electric Network: A combination of various electric elements, connected in any manner what's ever, is called an electric network.

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Kirchhoff's current law (KCL):

In any electrical network, the algebraic sum of the currents meeting at a point is zero.

Example:

$I_1, I_4 =$ incoming current
 $I_2, I_3, I_5 =$ outgoing current.

$$I_1 + (-I_2) + (-I_3) + I_4 + (-I_5) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 - I_2 - I_3 + I_4 - I_5 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow I_1 + I_4 = I_2 + I_3 + I_5$$

Kirchhoff's voltage law (KVL):

The algebraic sum of the products of currents and resistances in each of the conductors in any closed path in a network plus the algebraic sum of the e.m.f.s in that path is zero.

In other words, $\sum IR + \sum e.m.f = 0$

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Example:

$$- I_1 R_1 - I_2 R_2 + I_3 R_3 - I_4 R_4 - E_2 + E_1 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow - I_1 R_1 - I_2 R_2 + I_3 R_3 - I_4 R_4 = E_2 - E_1$$

Superposition Theorem:

In a network of linear resistances containing more than one generator, the current which flows at any point is the sum of all the currents which would flow at that point if each generator were considered separately and all the other generators replaced for the time being by the resistances equal to their internal resistances.

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Fig - (a)

Fig - (b)

In figure (b), 12v battery has been removed and replaced by 1Ω .

There are two parallel path between A & B.
having 6Ω and $(2+1) = 3\Omega$ resistance.

$$\therefore \text{Equivalent resistance} = 6 \parallel 3 = 2\Omega$$

$$\text{Total resistance} = (0.5 + 2.5 + 2)\Omega = 5\Omega$$

$$\therefore I_1' = \frac{6}{5} \text{ A} = 1.2 \text{ A}$$

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$$I' = 1.2 \times \frac{3}{9} \quad \left[\begin{array}{l} 3 = \text{opposite resistance} \\ 9 = \text{total resistance} \end{array} \right]$$

$$= 0.4 \text{ A}$$

$$I_2' = 1.2 \times \frac{6}{4}$$

$$= 0.8 \text{ A}$$

Again,

Fig(c)

In figure-(c), 6 volt battery has been removed but not its internal resistance.

The equivalent resistance to the left of

$$A \& B = 3 \parallel 6 = 2 \Omega$$

$$\therefore \text{Total resistance} = (1+2) \Omega = 5 \Omega$$

$$\therefore I_2'' = 12/5 = 2.4 \text{ A}$$

At point A current divide into two part-

$$I_1'' = 2.4 \times \frac{3}{9} = 0.8 \text{ A}$$

$$I_2'' = 2.4 \times \frac{6}{9} = 1.6 \text{ A}$$

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$$I_1 = I_1' - I_1'' = 0$$

$$= 1.2 - 1.6$$

$$= -0.4 A$$

$$I_2 = I_2' - I_2'' = 2.4 - 0.8$$

$$= 1.6 A$$

$$I = I' + I''$$

$$= 0.4 + 0.8$$

$$= 1.2$$

Voltage drop across $6\Omega = 6 \times 1.2$
 $= 7.2 V$

Ques 2 Exam which is the
 first exam after Eid
 Time: 30 minutes.

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Ex: By using superposition theorem, find the current in resistance R shown in figure.

Internal resistance of cell, are negligible.

$$R_{AC} = 1 \parallel 0.04 = 1 \times \frac{0.04}{1.04} = 0.038 \Omega$$

$$\text{Total resistance} = 0.05 + 0.038 = 0.088 \Omega$$

$$\therefore I = \frac{2.05}{0.088} = 23.3 \text{ A}$$

$$I_1 = 23.3 \times \frac{0.04}{1.04} = 0.896 \text{ A}$$

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$$ABC \parallel ADC = 1 \parallel 0.05 = 1 \times \frac{0.05}{1.05} = 0.048 \Omega$$

$$\text{Total resistance} = 0.04 + 0.048 = 0.088 \Omega$$

$$\therefore I = \frac{2.15}{0.088} = 24.4 \text{ A}$$

$$I_2 = 24.4 \times \frac{0.05}{1.05} = 1.16 \text{ A}$$

$$\therefore \text{Total current through } 1.05 \Omega = I_1 + I_2 = (0.896 + 1.16) \text{ A} = 2.056 \text{ A}$$

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Thevenin Theorem:

P-108
Electrical Tech
D.L. Thevenin -

$$V_{oc} = \text{Drop across } R_2 = IR_2 = \frac{ER_2}{R_1 + R_2 + r}$$

$$I = \frac{E}{R_1 + R_2 + r}$$

$$V_{oc} \text{ thevenin voltage} = V_{th}$$

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Again,

$$R = R_2 \parallel (R_1 + r) = \frac{R_2 (r_1 + r)}{R_2 + (R_1 + r)}$$

The venion resistance = R_{th}

$$I = \frac{V_{th}}{R_{th} + R_L}$$

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Theoretical question:

- (i) The equivalent of emf. when viewed from A & B
- (ii) The equivalent resistance.
- (iii) Current in the load resistance R_L of 15Ω

$$I = \frac{24}{1+3+12} = 1.5 \text{ A}$$

$$V_{oc} = 12 \times 1.5 = 18 \text{ V}$$

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$$R_{th} = 12 \times \frac{4}{12+4} = 3\Omega$$

(12)

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore I &= \frac{V_{th}}{R_{th} + R_L} \\ &= \frac{18}{15 + 3} \\ &= 1A \text{ Ans.} \end{aligned}$$

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Resistance in Parallel :

How $\Rightarrow \frac{V}{R_1} + \frac{V}{R_2} + \frac{V}{R_3} = \frac{V}{R}$

(i) Potential difference across all resistance is same (V)

How $\Rightarrow \frac{V}{R_1} + \frac{V}{R_2} + \frac{V}{R_3} = \frac{V}{R}$

(ii) Current in each resistor is different and is given by ohm's law.

(iii) The total current is the sum of the three separate current.

$$I = I_1 + I_2 + I_3 = \frac{V}{R_1} + \frac{V}{R_2} + \frac{V}{R_3}$$

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Voltage divided rule:

$$\text{Total resistance } R = R_1 + R_2 + R_3 = 2 + 4 + 6 = 12 \Omega$$

$$V_1 = V \cdot \frac{R_1}{R} = 24 \times \frac{2}{12} = 4 \text{ volt}$$

$$V_2 = V \cdot \frac{R_2}{R} = 24 \times \frac{4}{12} = 8 \text{ volt}$$

$$V_3 = V \cdot \frac{R_3}{R} = 24 \times \frac{6}{12} = 12 \text{ volt}$$

Show, $V = V_1 + V_2 + V_3$

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(1) Current is the same through all three conductors.

(2) Voltage drop across each is different due to its different resistance and is given by ohm's law

(3) Sum of all three voltage drop is equal to the voltage applied across the three conductors.

$$V = V_1 + V_2 + V_3$$

$$= IR_1 + IR_2 + IR_3$$

But $V = IR$

$$\therefore IR = IR_1 + IR_2 + IR_3$$

$$\Rightarrow R = R_1 + R_2 + R_3$$

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Principle of Electronics

v.k. sabbir

Fargo. Tarzique Islam
CSE Dept.

Ohm's Law: The ratio of potential difference (V) between any two points on a conductor to the current (I) flowing through them, is constant, provided that temperature of the conductor does not change.

For other words, $\frac{V}{I} = \text{constant}$

or, $\frac{V}{I} = R$, where R is the resistance of the conductor.

Resistance in series:

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Insulator:

Conductor:

Semiconductor:

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3rd E. band
2nd E. band
1st E. band

Most group.

Valence band :

The range of energies (ie band) powered by valence electron is known as valence band.

conduction band
↑
forbidden energy gap (V)
↓
Valence band

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Handwritten notes and diagrams on a piece of paper. At the top, there is a calculation for impedance: $Z_i = \text{Impedance}$ and $Z_L =$. Below this is a circuit diagram showing a voltage source of 100V, a resistor of 100Ω, and a load resistor of 100Ω. The text "Atomic structure:" is written above a diagram of an atom with a central nucleus and two energy levels labeled "1st E.L." and "2nd E.L.". Below the atom diagram is a schematic of a three-level energy system with levels labeled "1st E.L.", "2nd E.L.", and "3rd E.L.". Resistors R_1 , R_2 , and R_3 are shown connected to these levels. A downward arrow points from the atom diagram to the energy level diagram.

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Here, $E_g = 500V$ (voltage source)

$$R_i = 1000\Omega$$

$$R_{L1} = 10\Omega \quad I_1 = ?$$

$$R_{L2} = 100\Omega \quad I_2 = ?$$

$$I_1 = \frac{E_g}{R_i + R_{L1}} = \frac{500}{1000 + 10} = 495A$$

$$I_2 = \frac{E_g}{R_i + R_{L2}} = \frac{500}{1000 + 100} = 454A$$

Alternating voltage source:

$$I = \frac{E_g}{Z_L + Z_i}$$

$$V = (E_g - IZ_i)$$

$$\text{or } IZ_v$$

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$$I = \frac{V}{R}$$

load current, $I = \frac{E_g}{R_L + R_i}$

Terminal voltage, $V = (E_g - IR_i)$ or IR_L

Ex: Battery

+-
single battery

|||+-
multi battery

1.2

A d.c source generating 500 V has an internal resistance of 1000Ω. Find load current if load resistance is (i) 10Ω and (ii) 100Ω

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Free electrons:

The valence electrons which are very loosely attached to the nucleus are known as free electrons.

Voltage sources:

1. Direct voltage source:

R_i = Internal resistance of DC source.

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Former Dyeing Officer, Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;
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Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023cm). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024a). *Advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Engineering.* <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>;
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.*
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;
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- Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

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Hossain, M. A. (2024i). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research

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manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; enr.anowar@yahoo.com.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;
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Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;
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Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>;
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Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

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- Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is self-approaching for the prestigious 'best researcher award' under the provisional nomination of organizing committee, research scientist awards of Indian government [Grant].* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36413.17128>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064119>
- Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is requesting to Mr. António Guterres, Secretary-General of United Nations for a legal stipend or legal award to proceed with legal proceeding of life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35976.12805>;
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<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/A-cost-minimization-process-of-heat-and-energy-for-Hossain-Samanta/145246a45b40a7ef33c3e37cc99083f91f6555fa>;
<http://dx.doi.org/10.15406/jteft.2019.05.00207>

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Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, D. S., Barrister (Dr.). (2025). *Journal of Dr. Anowar.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29003.30243>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15550150>

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